

Impact of Consumer Buying Behavior Behavior and Marketing Psychology: A Case study of Selsun Blue shampoo

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Abstract

This research Investigates Impact of Consumer Buying Behavior Behavior and Marketing Psychology: A Case study of Selsun Blue shampoo. Data were collected from various secondary sources i.e annual reports and magazines. Data were analyzed by using SPSS-24-Version. It was revealed that Selsun Blue is one of the largest anti-dandruff shampoo brands in the FMCG category. The company has recently facing a challenging crisis with a historic low on sales and waning customer loyalty. Analysis of the current situation has led to the conclusion that the company's marketing strategy is misaligned with factors that influence consumer behavior. There is a need to conduct consumer surveys and tap into the psychological factors that govern the behavior of consumers. These factors include individual, perception, attitude, motivation, and cultural factors. The demographic and psychographic variables also play a part in affecting consumer decisions. Keeping these factors in view, Selsun Blue needs to understand the needs of consumers more deeply and target the right customers through the right segmentation. It is recommended, after detailed analysis, that the company should rebrand itself through a new packaging and lower pricing. Clear information regarding the product's main features should be provided on the packaging it, as FMCG products can be advertised on the shelf on supermarkets while consumers are searching through the aisles. The company should also focus more on enhancing the sales volume rather and improve revenue this way. This would enable the company to attract more customers and gain their loyalty, which is the main problem that it is currently experiencing. With these strategies, correctly executed, there is little reason why Selsun Blue, a genuinely effective anti-dandruff shampoo brand, should not become the favorite choice of consumers in the market. Lastly, the company can also take advantage of research studies that establish Selsun Blue as a more effective brand compared to its competitors. This can improve the credibility that customers can feel for the brand and thus increase repeat sales for the product at the hands of satisfied customers.

Introduction

the FMCG product under consideration in this report is Selsun Blue shampoo. It is an over-the-counter shampoo for alleviating dandruff and seborrheic dermatitis. The product is considered one of the most effective treatments for something as persistent as dandruff. Selsun Blue is not the only dandruff product in the market. Its main competitors include Clear and Head & Shoulders. Both of these brands have a strong customer base. However, Selsun Blue has the support of a research study that demonstrates its greater effectiveness in controlling dandruff than other tested shampoo brands.

Selsun Blue is therefore placed as one of the leading brands in the dandruff shampoo market which allows it to retain customers and attract new ones easily. Being an FMCG product, it has a short shelf-life and thus the sales volume is naturally high. Consumers in the FMCG market exhibit different kinds of behaviors than in other markets. This is due to the fast moving nature and small shelf-life of these products. In addition, FMCG products are also quite cheap. As a result, consumers do not have to perform the same level of research on the product which they would have to perform for higher-priced and more expensive products.

Thus, with the nature of the product in mind, this report will assess the current marketing mix and strategy of the company and how well it is aligned with consumer behavior theory. To objective is to promote sales further and take advantage of knowledge of consumer psyche to achieve this task.

According to Cavanaugh (2018), the problem of consumer behavior is usually investigated in close connection with the problem and the options for segmenting consumers. There are many reasons for carrying out the typology of consumers, and therefore their behavior. Consumers are looking for the benefits of a product or service. Benefits can be economic, psychological, hedonic, or social. The behavior of the buyer at the same time has a direct impact on both personal factors, and socio-cultural: education, social status, status, roles etc. Accordingly, a number of criteria for the typologization of consumer behavior have an objective, relatively easy to record: by the purpose of the goods, sex, age, income, educational level, professional status of the consumer. Roy and Ray (2017) highlight the influence of the environment: cultural, ethnic, socially-status, family, situational; tools and mechanisms of trade impact, consumer protection.

Other consumer behavior criteria (psychographic) are based on the study of psychological and behavioral responses and characteristics of people: the speed of acceptance of goods to consumption, the degree of adherence to a particular brand,

psychological types of personality and lifestyles, motivation - right up to the general atmosphere in which the psyche of certain generations of consumers was formed (Stephen, 2016). The consumer choice is made from the "selection package", which is part of the "awareness kit", which in turn is part of the "complete set". Before making their choice, the consumer consciously or more often unconsciously runs through the "ladder of choice", at the base of which lie the desires or needs of the consumer and at the top the competing brands (Zhao, Gao, Wu, Wang, and Zhu, 2014).

Since Selsun Blue has suffered a huge blow to customer loyalty of late, there is a direct need for the company to reevaluate its marketing efforts. According to Petit, Spence, Velasco, Woods, and Cheok (2017), a decline in customer loyalty is a logical result of competitors offering better products and more value. There is no doubt that the formula that Selsun Blue uses for treating dandruff is quite effective and does in fact lead to positive results for the consumers.

Nonetheless, customers are still not as satisfied with the brand as they are with others.

To address this issue, the company should first conduct a market survey and understand the deeper mechanism of consumer behavior. According to Jones Christensen, Siemsen, and Balasubramanian (2015), perception is one of the most important factors that influence the behavior of consumers. The survey in previous assessment also established that perception is a key determinant of a consumer's decision-making. To restore some of the lost loyalty from customers, Selsun Blue should redirect its energy and efforts into advertisement and marketing appeals to the visual senses: such as packaging. As Murphy and Dweck (2016) note, the primary function of packaging is to visually impress consumers.

As such, Selsun Blue could emanate the persona that it is now a revamped product that is all set for offering customers value which it was unable to before. Champniss et al. (2017) supports the view that pricing and packaging should be given special importance for FMCG products,

Research Methodology

Data were collected from various secondary sources i.e annual reports and magazines. Data were analyzed by using SPSS-24-Version

1. Occupants are market participants (those who make purchases on the market);
2. Objects - market items (products and items that are bought and sold on the market, as well as the presence of unmet needs);
3. Objectives - the goals that market participants set for themselves (why they buy);
4. Organisations - organizations present in the market (those who interact with consumers on the market);
5. Operations - the operational processes of the market (how purchases are made);
6. Occasions - acquisition opportunities (when purchases are made);
7. Outlets - sales channels (where purchases are made).

Results

Consumer behavior is a matter of interest to marketers because it can help them answer questions such as how the consumer will decide and what decision will be made by him depending on the effect of several groups of factors; awareness of the problem, a sense of need; situational factors of influence: social and physical environment, the time factor and the previous state; psychological factors: personality structure, values, beliefs, lifestyle, selectivity of perception, training, commitment to the brand, brand; socio-cultural factors: the action of "opinion leaders", families, other reference groups and social classes, "word of mouth"; information factors: the availability of information and the ability to determine the value of the Data were collected from Various secondary sources i.e annual reports and magazines.

Consumer behavior is an important discipline for modern marketers. According to Godey et al. (2016), consumer decision-making processes and accompanying psychological processes and functions involve awareness of needs, search and evaluation of options, perception of the purchasing process, consumption, and satisfaction and avoidance of addictions. In addition, individual differences between consumers (in their knowledge, perception and motivation, values and lifestyles) and the flow of psychological processes (information processing, training, exposure to advertising, etc.) are all important factors that influence consumer decision-making

The FMCG products are no different in this regard when it comes to the behavior of consumers who have a need to buy said products. In this scenario, the Selsun Blue shampoo addresses the need of customers to alleviate their dandruff and improve the condition of their scalp. The underlying motivation for the consumer could be manifold. For instance, consumers might be persuaded to buy the shampoo as an attempt to improve their self-esteem if the persistence of dandruff is something that distresses them emotionally. Since these are products that can advertise themselves on the shelf

while consumers go ruffling through supermarkets and stores. If consumers come across a neatly packaged product that they find affordable, they are likely to give it a try and purchase it even if they do not actually need it (Couture, Arcand, Sénécal, and Ouellet, 2015). This is where Selsun Blue has been lacking, failing to adjust to the situation and simply continuing the same marketing tactics which have led to company to the current crisis.

The company should also take into account the demographic and psychographic characteristics of customers and perform segmentation accordingly. The advertisement and marketing campaigns should be designed in such a way so as to appeal to the population to which the product is most relevant. In the present scenario, this implies that those customers fitting the demographic criteria for the product should be targeted. This would involve the younger generations in the age bracket of 18-34, which are, as a rule, more susceptible to suffer from dissatisfaction with their self-image. Dandruff is known to affect the self-esteem of individuals and this effect is more pronounced among women than men (Xu et al., 2017).

As such, Selsun Blue should make advertisements that address how the product can help sufferers control dandruff and therefore improve their confidence in society. The advertisements should involve young individuals in social settings that most individuals are likely to find themselves in. The idea is to allow prospective customers to relate to the advertisements and persuade them that this product can meet their need of controlling dandruff. However, this can only be effectively done if the company undertakes a proper analysis of consumer behavior and the factors that influence those (Lee et al., 2015).

In assessment 2, a survey was conducted which highlighted that motivation, perception, and attitude of consumers are some of the most important factors that govern their behavior when it comes to consumption patterns. This knowledge should be taken advantage of by the company and it should form the foundation on which marketing decisions are made for better alignment to consumer behavior (Murphy and Dweck, 2016). The awareness stage for every consumer is one of the most critical ones, since this is where a consumer acknowledges their need for something and thus looks for a product to eliminate the need. It is in this stage that Selsun Blue should seek to implant desirability for the product among consumers in order to increase rate of conversion of prospects into customers and securing their loyalty in the long-term (Petit et al., 2017).

Once a consumer has become aware of the need, they naturally progress towards the research phase whereby different products capable of meeting the need of the consumer are evaluated. Competitors in the FMCG shampoo market are quite strong and are capable of gaining customers with the quality of their product and marketing campaigns. Selsun Blue should utilize the opportunity to spread awareness among consumers regarding actual scientific studies that have shown its product to be more effective in treating dandruff than the products of competitors. This can significantly improve the perception the public has for the product and increase credibility of Selsun Blue as a genuinely effective product.

Finally, Selsun Blue should reduce its pricing and aim towards increasing the sales volume rather than maintaining a high profit margin. This strategy would have two effects: first, if successfully implemented, it would lead to an increase in sales as the company's entire objective would revolve around boosting sales and generating more revenue as a result.

Secondly, a higher sales volume is necessarily a result of repeat purchases and the expansion of the customer base (Cavanaugh, 2018). Therefore, this strategy would enable Selsun Blue to overcome its declining sales and poor customer loyalty.

Conclusions

Selsun Blue is one of the best FMCG anti-dandruff shampoos in the market. Although the product is currently undergoing a difficult phase owing to a lack of informed marketing strategy, the company can regain its lost status and customers through a revitalized approach to marketing, targeting the right customers through acknowledge of consumer behavior patterns across different demographics and influencing their decision-making through packaging, pricing, and a sales-oriented strategy. Selsun Blue should start its revamping strategy by first rebranding its product. To achieve this rebranding, the company should develop a new packaging with different colors. Moreover, its package should contain more informative content regarding the constituents and distinguishing characteristics of the product. This would help consumers decide whether they should purchase the product merely by reading information on the packaging. The modern consumer is much more informed that they used to be until the decade (Monteiro, 2018). This is due to the availability of Internet as a knowledge and research resource that virtually anyone can use. As such, companies that respect the literacy of their consumers are more likely attract the goodwill of the customers.

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